

Non-Stationary Markov Decision Processes and Continual Reinforcement Learning Algorithms

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Certificate of Examination

This is to certify that the dissertation titled “*Non-Stationary Markov Decision Processes and Continual Reinforcement Learning Algorithms*” submitted by Mr. Katakam Sandesh(Registration No. 20062) for the partial fulfillment of the BS-MS dual degree program of the Institute, has been examined by thesis committee duly appointed by the Institute. The committee finds the work done by the candidate satisfactory and recommends that the report be accepted.

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Declaration

The work presented in this dissertation has been carried out by me under the guidance of Dr.Srijith P.K at the Indian Institute of Technology, Hyderabad. This work has not been submitted in part or in full for a degree, a diploma, or a fellowship to any other university or institute. Whenever contributions of others are involved, every effort is made to indicate this clearly. This thesis is a bona fide record of original work done by me and all sources listed within have been detailed in the bibliography.

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This is to certify that Katakam Sandesh, student of BS-MS (10th Semester) of the Department of Mathematical Sciences at Indian Institute of Science Education and Research Berhampur has carried out the dissertation titled, “Non-Stationary Markov Decision Processes and Continual Reinforcement Learning Algorithms” under my supervision for the partial fulfillment of his BS-MS Degree. The thesis has been examined with the Turnitin software and is found to be within the limit of the plagiarism policy of the Department of Mathematical Sciences, Indian Institute of Science Education and Research, Berhampur.

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Abstract

Non-stationarity is a key challenge in sequential decision-making problems, affecting how learning algorithms adapt over time. Modern sequential decision-making algorithms do not fully account for non-stationarity in MDPs, even though it is a common challenge in real-world problems. In this thesis, we study and devise methods based on gradient alignment and sampled replay memory to learn an optimal policy π_t^* over a sequence of Markov Decision Processes (MDPs) $\{\mathcal{M}\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$ where the components of MDPs $\langle \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, r \rangle$ may change over time t . A primary challenge in Continual reinforcement learning is to mitigate a well-known problem called "catastrophic forgetting". Given a sequence of MDPs $\{\mathcal{M}\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$ with corresponding optimal policies $\{\pi_t^*\}$, catastrophic forgetting can be thought of as a decrease in expected return $\mathcal{J}(\pi^*; \mathcal{M}_\tau)$ for $\tau < t$ when learning π_t . In this regard, we aim to develop MDP algorithms to address this issue while ensuring fast adaptation from previous task to current task in RL. We build on existing class of methods that reduce gradient interference and ensuring gradient alignment during the learning process so as to avoid catastrophic forgetting while initializing the next task with good inductive priors for fast adaptation.

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Notation

Symbol	Description
\mathcal{S}	State space
\mathcal{A}	Action space
$\mathcal{P}(s' s, a)$ or P	Transition probability (dynamics)
$r(s, a)$	Reward function
γ	Discount factor, $\gamma \in [0, 1)$
μ	Initial state distribution
$\pi(a s)$	Policy (probability of taking action a in state s)
$\mathcal{V}^\pi(s)$	Value function of policy π at state s
$\mathcal{Q}^\pi(s, a)$	Action-value function of policy π at (s, a)
$\mathcal{A}^\pi(s, a)$	Advantage function, $\mathcal{Q}^\pi(s, a) - \mathcal{V}^\pi(s)$
τ	A task or a trajectory (depending on context)
$\mathcal{J}(\pi)$	Expected return of policy π
θ	Parameters of a neural network (policy/value)
α	Inner loop learning rate (MAML)
β	Outer loop learning rate (MAML)
T	Bellman operator
T^π	Bellman operator for policy π
$\mathcal{M} = (\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, r, \gamma, \mu)$	A Markov Decision Process (MDP)
\mathcal{M}_{CRL}	Continual reinforcement learning problem
$f(i, t)$	Time-dependent component in non-stationary MDPs
\mathcal{T}_i	Task i in a sequence of tasks

Table 1: Summary of Notation used in this Thesis

Chapter 1

Introduction

Reinforcement learning popularly known as learning from experience has shown success across a varied range of domains, from playing complex games to robotic control. Most of the sequential decision making problems can be posed as RL problems. However the current progress heavily focused on problem settings where they assume stationarity of MDP components. In real world scenarios, this assumption doesn't hold and environments evolve due to external influences, interaction and shifts in objectives. This leads to **Non-Stationary MDPs**. Before mathematically defining our problem setting, we would like to give a more general formulation followed from Khetarpal et al. [15] Continual Reinforcement learning is characterized by agent that must learn and adapt continuously across a sequence of tasks or evolving environments. As noted by Khetarpal et al. [15], we can formally define this as:

(Continual RL Problem \mathcal{M}_{CRL}): [15]

Let the state space be \mathcal{S} , action space be \mathcal{A} together with an observation space \mathcal{O} and a reward function $r : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and the transitions in the MDP is governed by $p : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}$ along with an observation function (to extend the generalization to POMPDs), $x : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{O}$. Then, general continual reinforcement learning problem can be given as:

$$\mathcal{M}_{\text{CRL}} \doteq \langle S(t), A(t), r(t), p(t), x(t), O(t) \rangle, \quad (1.1)$$

*where each component is allowed to change with time t and the functional form $f(i, t)$ where i is the input for each component of MDP is assumed to be **Lipschitz Continuous** and **Piece-wise Non-stationary***

Problem Definition

In this thesis, we focus on a special case of the above general formulation where across sequence of tasks $\{\tau\}_{i=1}^t$, both transition function $\mathcal{P}(s'|s, a)$ and $r(s, a)$ are allowed to vary and the goal is to learn a policy π^* that performs well not just on a single task but across the entire task sequence.

$$\mathcal{M}_{\text{CRL}} \doteq \langle S, A, r(t), p(t) \rangle, \quad (1.2)$$

Core challenges in Continual RL: Forgetting and Transfer

- **Catastrophic Forgetting:** Let $\mathcal{T}_1, \mathcal{T}_2, \mathcal{T}_3, \dots, \mathcal{T}_t$ be a sequence of tasks. Catastrophic forgetting is observed when the performance of the learned policy π_t on earlier tasks \mathcal{T}_i for $i < t$ is significantly worse than its performance immediately after learning \mathcal{T}_i . It is measured by **Forgetting Measure**(\mathcal{F}_i)
- **Forward Transfer:** measures how learning earlier tasks **enables faster convergence on future tasks**. For two tasks, \mathcal{T}_i and \mathcal{T}_j , $i < j$, forward transfer occurs if training on \mathcal{T}_i accelerates performance on \mathcal{T}_j compared to just learning \mathcal{T}_j
- **Backward Transfer:** It occurs if learning policy π over task \mathcal{T}_j in a sequence improves performance on task \mathcal{T}_i where $i < j$

Drawbacks of Existing Methods

While several methods have been proposed to tackle this problem in continual learning literature most suffer from fundamental limitations when applied to non-stationary MDPs.

- **Memory Replay Based Methods:** Maintain a memory buffer of past experiences and replay during learning. Examples: Experience replay in DQN.
 - Suffers from scalability issue as the **memory size grows with number of tasks**.
 - **No Forward Transfer/Fast Adaptation to future tasks in the sequence**

- **Regularization Based Methods:** imposes constraints on parameter updates to preserve important weights learned during previous tasks
 - Sensitive to task boundaries
 - **Lack Forward Transfer** and **Under-fitting on new tasks**
- **Gradient Projection and Interference:** Recent methods like **GEM** and **A-GEM** address catastrophic forgetting by modifying the learning objective to minimize gradient interference between tasks.
 - **Doesn't scale well** with RL algorithms like PPO, SAC etc.
 - **Doesn't tackle backward transfer problem** in continual RL

Motivation

Our motivation for solving this problem is two fold:

Real-world application of RL rarely occurs in stationary setting. For example, an autonomous vehicle encounters new driving conditions every day and in health care application non-stationarity arises due to seasonal disease patterns, emergent conditions. In recommender systems, user preferences evolve especially in streaming domains and e-commerce

Continual Learning methods in supervised learning is heavily studied and various methods were proposed for the supervised setting which include replay based(storing samples in memory), regularization based(Elastic weight consolidation(EWC)), Gradient alignment (GEM and A-GEM) etc. However translating these methods directly to reinforcement learning (RL) is non-trivial. Unlike supervised learning, RL doesn't assume the entire data is available before training. The agent is responsible for data collection based on the current policy during training and the policy gradient updates in RL tend to have high variance even within a single task. In continual setting, where tasks arrive sequentially and there is a distributional shift in dynamics and rewards, this variance gets amplified and the instability blows up.

Hence, its important to study and devise methods for Non-stationary MDPs and continual RL problem setting.

Proposed Solution

To address the drawbacks of existing methods in continual RL, we propose an adaptation of meta-learning based method called **Look-Ahead MAML** for continual RL. Previously this methods has been shown good results for continual learning setting. We chose to adapt this method for continual RL since they show in Gupta et al. [7] that gradient alignment combined with small replay memory can solve the core challenges in continual RL i.e. *catastrophic forgetting, forward transfer and backward transfer* In this thesis we derive the adaptations of Look Ahead MAML for three representative Deep RL algorithms: PPO, SAC and Rainbow DQN We hypothesize that look-ahead mechanism enables these algorithms to:

- Retain prior task performance (*mitigating catastrophic forgetting*)
- Adapt rapidly to new tasks (*promoting forward transfer*)
- Improve prior knowledge using new experiences (*promote backward transfer*)

A conceptual illustration of this mechanism is given below and is discussed in detail in chapter 5:

Figure 1.1: Comparison between Standard MAML and Look-Ahead MAML.

Left: In **Standard MAML**, the meta-learner adapts to a new task using a single inner-loop gradient step, updating the initial parameters θ to θ_t . This one-step adaptation is then used to compute the meta-objective for updating θ . *Right:* In **Look-Ahead MAML**, the meta-learner performs multiple simulated inner-loop updates $\theta \rightarrow \theta_t^{(1)} \rightarrow \theta_t^{(2)} \rightarrow \dots \rightarrow \theta_t^{(K)} \rightarrow \theta_t$. The meta-objective is computed based on the final adapted

parameters θ_t , after K look-ahead steps. This anticipatory mechanism allows the model to learn a more stable and generalizable initialization that is robust to extended gradient updates — a desirable property in continual reinforcement learning settings where task dynamics evolve and single-step adaptation may be brittle.

Overview of Chapters

This Thesis is divided in two parts: **Part I** goes over the background that is necessary for this thesis and **Part II** discusses literature review of continual RL methods and our proposed approach that is adapting look ahead MAML framework for RL algorithms(PPO, SAC and Rainbow-DQN)

Chapter 2 reviews Markov Decision Processes and we show a distinction between solution methods in two scenarios based on whether MDP model is known or unknown. In the former case, we have Value Iteration and Policy Iteration Methods and in the latter case we have sampling-based methods use samples to provide good estimates of the value function for solving the RL objective.

In Chapter 3, From analysis of existing literature, we develop a taxonomy of RL algorithms based on what quantity we focus on i.e. Value Function(DQN and Rainbow-DQN) or Policy (PPO). We motivate our selection of three representative algorithms: PPO (an on-policy for discrete/continuous action spaces), Rainbow-DQN (an off-policy for discrete actions), and SAC (an off-policy for continuous actions).

Chapter 4 reviews the continual reinforcement learning methods that are most effective, example: "Memory Replay based methods" and "Learning to Adapt". We also introduce the main issues to solve to achieve continual learning i.e. catastrophic forgetting and forward transfer. We also cover the gradient alignment based methods which modifies the general learning objective to mitigate the gradient interference while updating gradients across tasks

In Chapter 5, we introduce our proposed approach "Look Ahead MAML" Gupta et al. [7] inspired from results of the paper in supervised learning setting. We believe this method when employed for PPO, SAC and Rainbow DQN will solve the core challenges of continual RL

Chapter 6, will provide conclusions and insights of this thesis.

Part I: Background

Chapter 2

Markov Decision Processes

2.1 Discounted(Infinite-Horizon) MDP Setting

Markov Decision Processes (MDPs) are used to model problems in reinforcement learning. An Infinite-horizon Discounted Markov Decision Process(MDP) mathematically formulated as: $\mathcal{M} = (\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, r, \gamma, \mu)$ [2]. We employ this formulation to model sequential decision making problems in a given environment that undergoes transitions. An MDP consists of a State Space \mathcal{S} with either finite/infinite set of states, reward function that gives us reward after every transition and an objective that needs to be solved, which for now can be taken as discounted total expected reward or return. We now define the components of MDP and their notations:

- \mathcal{S} : State Space consists of set of states which maybe finite or infinite [2]
- \mathcal{A} : Action Space consists of set of actions which can be discrete or continuous. [2]
- \mathcal{P} : Transition probability $\mathcal{P} : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \Delta(\mathcal{S})$, where $\Delta(\mathcal{S})$ is all possible probability distributions over State space, \mathcal{S} . We define $\mathcal{P}(s'|s, a)$ is the probability of transitioning to state s' from s after taking action a [2]
- $r : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is the scalar Reward function, where $r(s, a)$ is reward obtained by taking action a in state s . In most cases that we encounter in this thesis $r(s, a)$ is deterministic but not limited to this we can have it as a random variable, which is the case in Distributional RL.

- γ : Discount factor assigns weight to future rewards, ensuring that the impact on the current decision-making process by future rewards are progressively reduced and $\gamma \in [0, 1)$
- $\mu \in \Delta(\mathcal{S})$: Initial State Distribution to generate initial state. We sample from this distribution to get an initial state. [2]

2.1.1 Important Terms associated with an MDP:

We begin by defining the most fundamental assumption underlying the Markov Decision Process (MDP) framework: the **Markov Property**. Following that we also define some important terms associated with an MDP and this gives us a good starting point to discuss MDP solution methods.

Definition 2.1.1 (Markov Property). *A sequence of random variables $\{S_t\}_{t \geq 0}$ satisfies the Markov property if, for any time step $t \geq 0$ and any collection of states s_0, s_1, \dots, s_{t+1} , the conditional probability of the next state S_{t+1} depends solely on the current state S_t and is independent of the full history. Formally,*

$$P(S_{t+1} = s_{t+1} \mid S_t = s_t, S_{t-1} = s_{t-1}, \dots, S_0 = s_0) = P(S_{t+1} = s_{t+1} \mid S_t = s_t).$$

- **Trajectory:** The sequence of transitions for a given MDP $\mathcal{M} = \langle \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, r, \gamma, \mu \rangle$ at time t

$$\tau_t = \{s_0, a_0, r_0, s_1, \dots, s_t, a_t, r_t\}$$

[2] is called a *trajectory*.

Here s_0 sampled from μ and at each time-step action a_t taken from \mathcal{A} and the reward for a transition at t is $r_t = r(s_t, a_t)$, while the next observed state s_{t+1} which is sampled from $\mathcal{P}(\cdot \mid s_t, a_t)$

- **Policies:** A *stationary policy* [2] is a mapping from current state (since it's markov we don't need history of states) to a space of all probability distributions over \mathcal{A} i.e. $\pi : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$. \mathcal{A} for deterministic and $\Delta(\mathcal{A})$ (distribution) for stochastic policies.

Important Note: An optimal policy is always a Markov Policy. So without loss

of generality, we can study markov policy instead of general policy(which depend on history of states)

- **Value (of some policy π):** The expected return of policy π in MDP \mathcal{M} when the initial state is sampled from μ [2] i.e.

Notation:

$$\mathcal{V}_h^\pi(s) = \mathbb{E}_\pi[\sum_{h'=h}^{\mathcal{H}} r_{h'}(s_{h'}, a_{h'}) | s_{h'} = s]$$

It computes total reward when we start from a state s and we are at step h and we follow the policy π from there on [2]

$\mathcal{Q}_h^\pi(s, a)$ (Q-Value of policy π at step h) = $\mathbb{E}_\pi[\sum_{h'=h}^{\mathcal{H}} r_{h'}(s_{h'}, a_{h'}) | s_{h'} = s, a_h = a]$ It computes total reward when we start from a state s and immediately take an action a at at step h and we follow the policy π from there on [2]

- **Goal in RL:** Find a policy π^* (**optimal policy**) that results in the maximum expected return for a trajectory, where return along a trajectory is:

$$\mathcal{R} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} [\gamma^i r(s_i, a_i)]$$

for trajectory τ

Alternatively, Find a π^* to maximize $v_1^\pi(s)$

Theorem 2.1.2. *For any General Policy π , there exists a markov policy μ such that,*

$$\mathcal{V}_1^\pi(s_1) = \mathcal{V}_1^*(s_1)$$

$\implies \exists$ an optimal policy that is Markov

Proof. (By Induction):

$$\mathcal{V}_h^\pi(s) = \sum_{h=1}^{\mathcal{H}} \mathbb{E}_\pi[r_h(s_h, a_h) | s_1]$$

Expand the expectation term,

$$\mathbb{E}_\pi[r_h(s_h, a_h) | s_1] = \sum_{h=1}^{\mathcal{H}} \sum_{s_h, a_h} \mathcal{P}_h^\pi(s_h, a_h | s_1)$$

where $\mathcal{P}_h^\pi(s_h, a_h | s_1)$ is probability at step h starting from state s following π

Construct a markov policy, that depend on general policies

Proof by Construction:

Construct μ where, μ_h is a markov policy, and general policy is given by $\mathbb{E}_\pi[\pi_h(a|\tau_h)]$,

where τ_h is trajectory $(s_0, a_0, \dots, s_h, a_h)$

$$\mu_h(a|s) = \mathbb{E}_\pi[\pi_h(a|\tau_h) | s_h = s]$$

Taking expectation over the entire τ_h

Defining Markov Policy,

$$\mu_h(a|s) = \begin{cases} \frac{\sum_{\tau_h, s_h=s} (\mathcal{P}_h^\pi(\tau_h \cdot \pi(a|\tau_h)))}{\mathcal{P}_h^\pi(s_h=s)} & \text{if } \mathcal{P}_h^\pi(s_h = s) \neq 0 \\ \text{arbitrary policy} & \text{if } \mathcal{P}_h^\pi(s_h = s) = 0 \end{cases}$$

Using Induction to prove the above Equation:

By our construction μ produces same visitation frequencies,

$$\mathcal{P}_h^\mu(s) = \mathcal{P}_h^\pi(s) \implies \mathcal{P}_h^\mu(s, a) = \mathcal{P}_h^\pi(s, a) \implies \mathcal{P}_{h+1}^\mu(s) = \mathcal{P}_{h+1}^\pi(s) \forall s$$

Base Case: $\mathcal{P}_1^\mu(s_1) = \mathcal{P}_1^\pi(s_1)$ is True ($\because s$ is fixed)

By Induction Hypothesis,

- $\mathcal{P}_h^\mu(s, a) = \mathcal{P}_h^\mu(s) \cdot \mu_h(a|s) = \text{LHS}$

$$\mathcal{P}_h^\pi(s, a) = \sum_{\tau_h, s_h=s} \mathcal{P}_h^\pi(\tau_h, a_h) = \sum_{\tau_h, s_h=s} \mathcal{P}_h^\pi(\tau_h) \pi(a|\tau_h) = \text{RHS}$$

By our construction both LHS = RHS

- $\mathcal{P}_{h+1}^\mu(s_{h+1}) = \sum_{s_h, a_h} \mathcal{P}_h^\mu(s_h, a_h, s_{h+1}) = \sum_{s_h, a_h} \mathcal{P}_h^\mu(s_{h+1} | s_h, a_h) \cdot \mathcal{P}_h^\mu(s_h, a_h)$

$$= \sum_{s_h, a_h} \mathcal{P}_h(s_{h+1} | s_h, a_h) \mathcal{P}_h^\pi(s, a)$$

$$= \mathcal{P}_{h+1}^\pi(s_{h+1})$$

Hence Proved

□

2.2 Bellman Consistency Equations

Establishes relation between \mathcal{V}^π and \mathcal{Q}^π . All stationary policies satisfy the following bellman consistency conditions:

Lemma 2.2.1 (Adapted from Agarwal et al. [2], 2019). *Assume that π is given as a stationary policy and we have both \mathcal{V}^π and \mathcal{Q}^π satisfying the following Bellman consistency equations for all $s \in \mathcal{S}, a \in \mathcal{A}$*

$$\mathcal{V}^\pi(s) = \mathcal{Q}^\pi(s, \pi(s))$$

$$\mathcal{Q}^\pi(s, a) = r(s, a) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{a \sim \pi(\cdot|s), s' \sim \mathcal{P}(\cdot|s, a)}[\mathcal{V}^\pi(s')]$$

Note: \mathcal{V}^π is a vector of magnitude $|\mathcal{S}|$ and \mathcal{Q}^π, r are vectors of magnitude $|\mathcal{S}| \cdot |\mathcal{A}|$

Corollary 2.2.2 (Adapted from Agarwal et al. [2], 2019). *Given that π is a stationary policy. We have :*

$$\mathcal{Q}^\pi = (\mathcal{I} - \gamma \mathcal{P}^\pi)^{-1} r$$

where \mathcal{I} is the identity matrix

2.2.1 Bellman Optimality Equations

For any choice of MDPs, we can show that there exists a stationary and deterministic policy that at the same time maximizes $\mathcal{V}^\pi(s)$ for all $s \in \mathcal{S}$. We can write it formally as theorem below:

Theorem 2.2.3 (Adapted from Agarwal et al. [2], 2019). *Given Π , the set of all non-stationary and random policies. We Define:*

$$\mathcal{V}^*(s) = \sup_{\pi \in \Pi} \mathcal{V}^\pi(s)$$

$$\mathcal{Q}^*(s, a) = \sup_{\pi \in \Pi} \mathcal{Q}^\pi(s, a)$$

which is finite since $\mathcal{V}^\pi(s)$ and $\mathcal{Q}^\pi(s, a)$ values are bounded between 0 and $\frac{1}{(1-\gamma)}$

We say there exists a stationary and deterministic policy π such that for all $s \in \mathcal{S}$ and $a \in \mathcal{A}$

$$\mathcal{V}^\pi(s) = \mathcal{V}^*(s)$$

$$\mathcal{Q}^\pi(s, a) = \mathcal{Q}^*(s, a)$$

we call such π as optimal policy

Theorem 2.2.4 (Adapted from Agarwal et al. [2], 2019). *(Bellman Optimality Equa-*

tions) For $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{S}||\mathcal{A}|}$ a vector will satisfy the Bellman optimality equations if:

$$Q(s, a) = r(s, a) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim \mathcal{P}(\cdot|s, a)} \left[\max_{a' \in \mathcal{A}} Q(s', a') \right]$$

For any vector $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{S}||\mathcal{A}|}$, we have that $Q = Q^*$ iff Q satisfies the Bellman optimality equations.

with respect to such Q^* if we infer a policy that is deterministic $\pi(s) \in \arg \max_{a \in \mathcal{A}} Q^*(s, a)$, then that $\pi(s)$ will be an optimal policy

Given these guarantees, we now introduce **Bellman Operator** which is crucial for proving convergence of Exact Solution Methods for MDPs that will be discussed in the next section

We can write one-step bellman update in terms of operator i.e The Bellman operator $T_M : \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{S}||\mathcal{A}|} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{S}||\mathcal{A}|}$. Each Bellman iteration can now be considered applying Bellman Operator to Q value like below:

$$TQ := r + \gamma \mathcal{P}V_Q$$

2.3 Solution Methods for MDPs

2.3.1 Exact Solution Methods

Value Iteration

In Value iteration, the algorithm iteratively applies a fixed point mapping with respect to Bellman operator T : We start at some Q , we apply T , the Bellman operator to Q as

$$Q \leftarrow TQ$$

Now, writing the Bellman Optimality Equations in a compact form:

$$Q = TQ$$

We refer to this algorithm as *Q-Value Iteration*

Lemma 2.3.1 (Bellman Operator as a Contraction). *Let $\mathcal{Q}, \mathcal{Q}' \in \mathbb{R}^{|\mathcal{S}||\mathcal{A}|}$ be two Q-value functions. The Bellman optimality operator T satisfies the following contraction property under the ∞ -norm:*

$$\|T\mathcal{Q} - T\mathcal{Q}'\|_\infty \leq \gamma \|\mathcal{Q} - \mathcal{Q}'\|_\infty,$$

where $\gamma \in [0, 1)$ denotes the discount factor.

Proof. For each state $s \in \mathcal{S}$, define the value function induced by \mathcal{Q} as $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}}(s) = \max_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \mathcal{Q}(s, a)$. The difference between value functions satisfies:

$$|\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}}(s) - \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}'}(s)| \leq \max_{a \in \mathcal{A}} |\mathcal{Q}(s, a) - \mathcal{Q}'(s, a)|.$$

Now consider the Bellman operator applied to both Q-functions. The ∞ -norm of their difference becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \|T\mathcal{Q} - T\mathcal{Q}'\|_\infty &= \|\mathcal{R} + \gamma\mathcal{P}\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}} - (\mathcal{R} + \gamma\mathcal{P}\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}'})\|_\infty \\ &= \gamma\|\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}} - \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}'})\|_\infty. \end{aligned}$$

Since the transition matrix \mathcal{P} is stochastic (rows sum to 1), it acts as a convex combination over states, so applying it cannot increase the maximum difference:

$$\|\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}} - \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}'})\|_\infty \leq \|\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}} - \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}'}\|_\infty.$$

Hence, we have:

$$\|T\mathcal{Q} - T\mathcal{Q}'\|_\infty \leq \gamma\|\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}} - \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}'}\|_\infty.$$

Finally, using the earlier bound:

$$\|\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}} - \mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{Q}'}\|_\infty \leq \|\mathcal{Q} - \mathcal{Q}'\|_\infty,$$

we conclude:

$$\|T\mathcal{Q} - T\mathcal{Q}'\|_\infty \leq \gamma\|\mathcal{Q} - \mathcal{Q}'\|_\infty.$$

□

Policy Iteration

Contrary to Value Iteration algorithm in Policy Iteration we start from an arbitrary policy π_0 , and repeat a two-step procedure for $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

- **Policy Evaluation:** During this step we *compute* Q^{π_k}
- **Policy Improvement:** After evaluating a policy at k th step we improve the policy i.e. *Update the policy:* $\pi_{k+1} = \pi_{Q^{\pi_k}}$

Lemma 2.3.2 (Adapted from Agarwal et al. [2], 2019). *Given Bellman Operator T and Q -value function Q , we have:*

- *Every successive policy after the improvement step is greater than Q^{π_k} and greater than or equal to applying Bellman Operator T for Q^{π_k} (equal at convergence). i.e*

$$Q^{\pi_{k+1}} \geq TQ^{\pi_k} \geq Q^{\pi_k}$$

- *The Q -Function corresponding to the updated policy π_{k+1} is closer to the optimal Q -Function Q^* in the ∞ -norm, with a contraction factor γ i.e.*

$$\|Q^{\pi_{k+1}} - Q^*\|_\infty \leq \gamma \|Q^{\pi_k} - Q^*\|_\infty$$

Proof. We begin by establishing that $TQ^* \geq Q^*$, where Q^* denotes the optimal action-value function and T is the Bellman optimality operator.

Since the policy improvement step in policy iteration produces deterministic policies, we know that $V^{\pi_k}(s) = Q^k(s, \pi_k(s))$ holds for every iteration k and state s . This leads us to:

$$\begin{aligned} TQ^*(s, a) &= r(s, a) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim P(\cdot|s, a)} \left[\max_{a'} Q^*(s', a') \right] \\ &\geq r(s, a) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim P(\cdot|s, a)} [Q^*(s', \pi_k(s'))] \\ &= Q^*(s, a), \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

which shows that $TQ^* \geq Q^*$ as desired.

Next, we aim to demonstrate that the updated estimate $Q^{k+1} \geq TQ^*$.

To begin, recall that by definition of Q^k under the greedy policy π_{k+1} , we have:

$$Q^k = r + \gamma P^{\pi_k} Q^* \leq r + \gamma P^{\pi_{k+1}} Q^* = \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t (P^{\pi_{k+1}})^t r = Q^{k+1}, \tag{2.2}$$

where the inequality follows from the fact that π_{k+1} is greedily chosen with respect to Q^k , and the equality uses the recursion for the expected return under the policy.

Using this fact, we evaluate:

$$\begin{aligned}
Q^{k+1}(s, a) &= r(s, a) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim P(\cdot|s, a)} [Q^{k+1}(s', \pi_{k+1}(s'))] \\
&\geq r(s, a) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim P(\cdot|s, a)} [Q^*(s', \pi_{k+1}(s'))] \\
&= r(s, a) + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{s' \sim P(\cdot|s, a)} \left[\max_{a'} Q^*(s', a') \right] \\
&= TQ^*(s, a),
\end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

which completes the argument for the first part of the proof.

We now move to the second claim concerning the ∞ -norm:

$$\begin{aligned}
\|Q^* - Q^{k+1}\|_\infty &\leq \|Q^* - TQ^*\|_\infty \\
&= \|TQ^* - TQ^k\|_\infty \\
&\leq \gamma \|Q^* - Q^k\|_\infty,
\end{aligned} \tag{2.4}$$

where the first inequality holds due to the result just proved that $Q^{k+1} \geq TQ^*$, and the final inequality follows from the contraction property of the Bellman operator T in the ∞ -norm.

□

2.3.2 ε -optimal policies

Let π represent a given policy, and π^* denote the optimal policy.

Definition 2.3.3 (ε -Suboptimal Policy). *A policy π is referred to as ε -suboptimal if its expected return is within ε of the optimal value function V^* , uniformly across all states. More precisely, for every state $s \in \mathcal{S}$, the following inequality holds:*

$$V^\pi(s) \geq V^*(s) - \varepsilon,$$

where $\varepsilon \geq 0$ denotes the allowed deviation from optimality and $V^\pi(s)$ is the value function corresponding to the policy π , and $V^*(s)$ is the optimal value function defined as $V^*(s) = \max_\pi V^\pi(s)$.

Note: If we are working with action-value functions, i.e. Q -functions, the definition of ϵ -optimality can be written using the Q -values. In this case, the condition becomes:

$$Q^\pi(s, a) \geq Q^*(s, a) - \epsilon, \forall (s, a) \in \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A}$$

In reinforcement learning, for most cases we consider the scenario where the model/transition function of MDP is not known to the learner. In the previous sections we established **Exact Solution Methods for MDPs** where the model is known and we proved convergence of those algorithms, but when the model of the MDP or transition kernel is not known to us we need to resort to sampling based methods where we collect sample transitions from an environment and use it to approximate \mathcal{V} or \mathcal{Q} functions (this is called model-free RL) or use sample transitions to approximate transition function ($\mathcal{P}(s'|s, a)$) (this is called model-based RL). These exact solution methods are also called **Tabular Methods**, since we need to store value for every state and action in a table which clearly **doesn't scale with large state and action spaces**. This also serves as our motivation for the use of function approximations for \mathcal{V} and \mathcal{Q} . We also shift our focus from optimal policy to ϵ -optimal policies (defined above) since the sampling based approximation can never reach the exact optimal policy.

Before we begin the next discussion. We introduce an MDP problem setting that we use for all the methods that are discussed in chapter 3 i.e. **Episodic Setting**

Definition 2.3.4 (Adapted from Agarwal et al. [2], 2019). **Episodic Setting:** *We consider episodes rather than entire trajectories in this setting. In each episode, the agent begins its interaction from an initial state s_0 drawn according to a fixed distribution μ , and proceeds for a bounded number of steps. After the episode concludes, the environment resets and the next trajectory also starts from a new sample $s_0 \sim \mu$, ensuring consistency in episode initialization. We can consider both finite-horizon or infinite-horizon cases:*

- (Finite Horizon MDPs): *Episodes lasts for H -steps, and after that the state resets to $s_0 \sim \mu$*
- (Infinite Horizon MDPs): *Episodes continues indefinitely with future rewards discounted by γ to ensure convergence of the return*

Definition 2.3.5 (Adapted from Agarwal et al. [2], 2019). (Advantage): *We also define*

the advantage $\mathcal{A}^{\pi(s,a)}$ of policy π

$$\mathcal{A}^{\pi(s,a)} := Q^{\pi(s,a)} - \mathcal{V}^{\pi(s)}$$

which is an important quantity useful in policy based methods in chapter 3

Chapter 3

Review and Taxonomy of RL Methods

3.1 Value Based Methods

Value Based Methods in RL focuses on learning good approximations of value functions from collected sample transitions in the environment during the training process. Value functions tell us how good it is for an agent to stay in a given state (\mathcal{V}) or to perform a given action from a state (\mathcal{Q}). We can implicitly infer the policy from a given state s at each iteration step when learning value functions by performing either greedy or ε -greedy approach on the values at that iteration. The class of Exact solution methods discusses in the previous chapter can also be considered value based methods. Some of the common value based methods that rely on function approximation and sample collection are: Q-Learning (also called as Off-Policy TD Learning), Deep Q-Networks etc.

3.1.1 Deep Q Learning

In Q-Learning [27], our objective is to learn the optimal action-value function Q^* :

$$Q^*(s, a) = \max_{\pi} \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t R(s_t, a_t) \mid s_0 = s, a_0 = a, \pi \right]$$

that satisfies the Bellman optimality equation:

$$Q^*(s, a) = \mathbb{E} \left[R(s, a) + \gamma \max_{a'} Q^*(s', a') \mid s, a \right]$$

[27]

Deep Q-Learning [18] is an extension of Q-Learning [27] method which uses neural networks(function approximations) to approximate Q-Values. Formally, $Q^*(s, a)$ is approximated using a neural network $Q(s, a; \theta)$, where θ are the parameters.

Given a sample transition from interaction with environment, we can collect (s, a, r, s') , we define our target as:

$$y = r + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(s', a'; \theta^-)$$

where θ^- are parameters of a target network

We use SGD (stochastic gradient descent) update steps to optimize the following loss function:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{(s,a,r,s') \sim \mathcal{D}} [(y - Q(s, a; \theta))^2]$$

The update rule for Deep Q Learning will be:

$$\theta \leftarrow \theta - \alpha \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}(\theta)$$

There are number of implementation details in DQN that are different from generic Q-Learning method which includes the use of **Experience Replay Buffer**(\mathcal{D}): which is used to store to further sample random mini-batches from \mathcal{D}

Actions are taken using an ε -**greedy policy** which can be written as:

$$a_t = \begin{cases} \text{sampled uniformly from } \mathcal{A}, & \text{with probability } \varepsilon, \\ \arg \max_{a \in \mathcal{A}} Q(s_t, a; \theta), & \text{with probability } 1 - \varepsilon, \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

3.1.2 Rainbow DQN: Improving DQN

Rainbow DQN is an improved version of DQN Algorithm introduced in the paper Hessel et al. [12]. This method adds several novel improvements to enhance performance and also provide stability for training in Deep RL. Hessel et al. [12] starts by taking the Double Q-Learning Algorithm from Hasselt et al. [11] paper this is done in order to address the overestimation bias in Q-learning. In the Double Q-Learning, the target network

becomes:

$$y = r + \gamma Q(s', \arg \max_{a'} Q(s', a'; \theta); \theta^-)$$

where θ are the current network parameters and θ^- are the target network parameters. It extends the implementation of Replay buffer in DQN by introducing **Prioritized Experience Replay** which samples transitions with respect to TD-error (temporal difference error) for that transition and every sample transition comes with a prioritization level α . It also uses the **Dueling Network Architecture** to decompose Q-value into state-value $\mathcal{V}(s)$ and advantage $\mathcal{A}(s, a)$

The most notable novelty of this method is the use of distribution of returns rather than just expected return (like in Distributional RL from Bellemare et al. [3]) and **Noisy Networks** to incorporate exploration through stochastic policies i.e. $a_t = \arg \max_a Q(s_t, a; \theta + \text{noise})$

Instead of estimating $Q(s, a)$ as a scalar in distributional version we consider full distribution over returns $\mathcal{Z}(s, a)$ and use cross entropy between target distribution $\Phi\mathcal{T}Z$ and the current predicted distribution \mathcal{Z}

$$\mathcal{L}_{C51}(\theta) = \text{CrossEntropy}(\Phi\mathcal{T}Z(s, a), Z(s, a; \theta))$$

For **Prioritized Experience Replay**, transitions are sampled with probability proportional to TD error:

$$P(i) = \frac{|\delta_i|^\alpha}{\sum_j |\delta_j|^\alpha}$$

and the **Importance sampling** of weights correct for the bias

$$w_i = \left(\frac{1}{N \cdot P(i)} \right)^\beta$$

Loss is weighted with w_i :

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{PER}} = w_i \cdot (y_i - Q(s_i, a_i; \theta))^2$$

A **Multi-Step Return** is evaluated using n -step cumulative reward:

$$y_t^{(n)} = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \gamma^k r_{t+k} + \gamma^n \max_{a'} Q(s_{t+n}, a'; \theta^-)$$

Algorithm 1 Rainbow DQN (Adapted from Hessel et al. [12])

Require: Experience memory \mathcal{D} , Q-network $Q(s, a; \theta)$, target network $Q(s, a; \theta^-)$

```
1: Randomly initialize weights  $\theta$ ; set  $\theta^- \leftarrow \theta$ 
2: for each training episode do
3:   Start from initial state  $s_0$ 
4:   while episode not terminated do
5:     Choose action  $a_t$  via  $\epsilon$ -greedy strategy w.r.t.  $Q(s_t, a; \theta)$ 
6:     Perform  $a_t$ , observe reward  $r_t$  and next state  $s_{t+1}$ 
7:     Save tuple  $(s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1})$  into replay buffer  $\mathcal{D}$ 
8:     Draw a batch  $\{(s_i, a_i, r_i, s'_i)\}_{i=1}^B$  using prioritized sampling
9:     for all samples in batch do
10:      Compute target value:

$$y_i = \begin{cases} r_i, & \text{if } s'_i \text{ is terminal} \\ r_i + \gamma \cdot Q(s'_i, \arg \max_{a'} Q(s'_i, a'; \theta); \theta^-), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

11:    end for
12:    Update online network by minimizing:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta) = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{i=1}^B (y_i - Q(s_i, a_i; \theta))^2$$

13:    if time step mod  $C = 0$  then
14:      Sync target network:  $\theta^- \leftarrow \theta$ 
15:    end if
16:  end while
17: end for
```

3.2 Policy Based Methods

In these methods, our main interest is to optimize a parameterized policy ($\pi_\theta(a|s)$) such that yields the highest possible expected return. The policy obtained is evaluated using

the value function evaluated from the initial state s_0 :

$$\mathcal{J}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}[\sum_{t=0}^T \gamma^t r_t]$$

where T stands for time-horizon and γ denotes the discount factor

3.2.1 Policy Gradient Theorem and REINFORCE

Let μ be a probability distribution over initial states. Define expected value function under optimal policy as:

$$\mathcal{V}^\pi(\mu) = \mathbb{E}_{s_0 \sim \mu}[\mathcal{V}^\pi(s_0)]$$

If we are considering a set of parameterized policies $\{\pi_\theta | \theta \in \Theta \subset \mathbb{R}^d\}$ where θ denotes the policy parameters. Our objective is to find a optimal policy i.e. the policy that maximizes the expected performance under the distribution μ :

$$\max_{\theta \in \Theta} \mathcal{V}^\pi(\mu)$$

This can be problem for policies that are not differentiable i.e. *deterministic policies*. So, Instead we avoid this problem by taking *stochastic policy classes* where we can differentiate the policy (necessary for deriving policy gradients). Some of the obvious choices we can take are:

Softmax Policies: $\pi_\theta(a|s) = \frac{\exp(\theta_{s,a})}{\sum_{a'} \exp(\theta_{s,a'})}$,

Likelihood Ratio Method

Suppose we define τ as a sequence of (s, a) pairs generated by a policy π starting from a state distribution μ . Then $P_\mu^\pi(\tau)$ (probability of observing τ under π):

$$P_\mu^{\pi_\theta}(\tau) = \prod_{t=0}^{\infty} \mu(s_t) \pi(a_t|s_t) P(s_{t+1}|s_t, a_t) \pi(a_{t+1}|s_{t+1})$$

We also define the **discounted return** of a trajectory τ , denoted by $\mathcal{R}(\tau)$

$$\mathcal{R}(\tau) := \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t r(s_t, a_t)$$

Now, the objective of interest will be expected return under policy π :

$$V^{\pi_\theta}(\mu) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim P_\mu^{\pi_\theta}} [R(\tau)]$$

Theorem 3.2.1. (Policy Gradients) [Adapted from Sutton et al. [24]]

Given an initial state distribution μ , the gradient of $V^{\pi_\theta}(\mu)$ can be expressed in several equivalent forms:

- **Monte Carlo form (REINFORCE):**

$$\nabla_\theta V^{\pi_\theta}(\mu) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim P_\mu^{\pi_\theta}} \left[R(\tau) \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta(a_t | s_t) \right]$$

- **Expression in terms of Action-Value Function:**

$$\nabla_\theta V^{\pi_\theta}(\mu) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim P_\mu^{\pi_\theta}} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t Q^{\pi_\theta}(s_t, a_t) \nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta(a_t | s_t) \right]$$

- **Expression in terms of Advantage Function:**

$$\nabla_\theta V^{\pi_\theta}(\mu) = \frac{1}{1-\gamma} \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d_\mu^{\pi_\theta}, a \sim \pi_\theta} [A^{\pi_\theta}(s, a) \nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta(a | s)]$$

Proof. We compute the gradient of the expected return under the optimal policy. Let π_θ be a stochastic policy parameterized by θ , and let τ denote a trajectory $(s_0, a_0, s_1, a_1, \dots)$ sampled under this policy. Define $R(\tau)$ as the total reward along trajectory τ , and $P_\mu^{\pi_\theta}(\tau)$ as the probability of that trajectory under initial state distribution μ .

$$\nabla V^{\pi_\theta}(\mu) = \nabla_\theta \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim P_\mu^{\pi_\theta}} [R(\tau)] = \sum_{\tau} R(\tau) \nabla_\theta P_\mu^{\pi_\theta}(\tau)$$

Applying the log-derivative (score function) trick:

$$= \sum_{\tau} R(\tau) P_\mu^{\pi_\theta}(\tau) \nabla_\theta \log P_\mu^{\pi_\theta}(\tau) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim P_\mu^{\pi_\theta}} \left[R(\tau) \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta(a_t | s_t) \right]$$

This gives us a trajectory-based gradient expression.

Next, to analyze the gradient of the state value function $V^{\pi_\theta}(s_0)$, we use the definition:

$$V^{\pi_\theta}(s_0) = \sum_{a_0} \pi_\theta(a_0 | s_0) Q^{\pi_\theta}(s_0, a_0)$$

Taking the gradient w.r.t. θ :

$$\nabla_{\theta} V^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_0) = \sum_{a_0} \nabla_{\theta} \pi_{\theta}(a_0 | s_0) Q^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_0, a_0) + \sum_{a_0} \pi_{\theta}(a_0 | s_0) \nabla_{\theta} Q^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_0, a_0)$$

Using the identity $\nabla_{\theta} \pi_{\theta} = \pi_{\theta} \nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}$, we rewrite:

$$= \sum_{a_0} \pi_{\theta}(a_0 | s_0) \nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a_0 | s_0) Q^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_0, a_0) + \sum_{a_0} \pi_{\theta}(a_0 | s_0) \nabla_{\theta} Q^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_0, a_0)$$

The second term can be expanded using the Bellman equation:

$$Q^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_0, a_0) = r(s_0, a_0) + \gamma \sum_{s_1} P(s_1 | s_0, a_0) V^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_1)$$

Thus,

$$\nabla_{\theta} Q^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_0, a_0) = \gamma \sum_{s_1} P(s_1 | s_0, a_0) \nabla_{\theta} V^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_1)$$

Now we substitute this back into the original $\nabla_{\theta} V^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_0)$:

$$\nabla_{\theta} V^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_0) = \sum_{a_0} \pi_{\theta}(a_0 | s_0) \nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a_0 | s_0) Q^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_0, a_0) + \gamma \sum_{a_0, s_1} \pi_{\theta}(a_0 | s_0) P(s_1 | s_0, a_0) \nabla_{\theta} V^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_1)$$

We can rewrite this recursively as:

$$\nabla_{\theta} V^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_0) = \mathbb{E}_{a_0 \sim \pi_{\theta}} [Q^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_0, a_0) \nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a_0 | s_0)] + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{a_0, s_1} [\nabla_{\theta} V^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_1)]$$

Taking expectation over $s_0 \sim \mu$, the initial state distribution will give us the gradient of the loss function w.r.t θ :

$$\nabla_{\theta} J(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{s_0 \sim \mu} [\nabla_{\theta} V^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_0)]$$

Writing this recursively over the full state-action distribution:

$$= \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{E}_{(s_t, a_t) \sim P_{\mu}^{\pi_{\theta}}} [\nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a_t | s_t) Q^{\pi_{\theta}}(s_t, a_t)]$$

This completes the derivation of the policy gradient using the log-derivative trick and Bellman recursion. \square

3.2.2 Natural Policy Gradient(NPG)

The standard policy gradient approach uses the gradient of $\mathcal{J}(\theta)$ to update parameters θ via gradient ascent, where the gradient is estimated using the *REINFORCE* trick or policy gradient theorem[24]:

$$\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{J}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{\pi_{\theta}}[\nabla_{\theta} \log \pi_{\theta}(a|s) \mathcal{Q}^{\pi}(s, a)]$$

from [24]

however this gradient doesn't give any information about the local geometry of the parameter space and that is why it treats all directions equally, even though π_{θ} has a lot of variance i.e. small changes in θ can result in moving further away from the optimal policy during policy updates. Kakade [13] addresses this issue by taking into account the information geometry of the policy space. Kakade [13] uses the natural gradient, which is the steepest ascent direction under the Fisher-Rao Riemannian metric instead of standard Euclidean distance. We can think of this method as an extension to the vanilla policy gradient methods that ensure stability between updates. In Kakade [13], they define a metric based on the underlying policy structure (with the help of fisher information matrix). Kakade [13] proves that by using this method we move towards choosing the same greedy optimal action as we do in policy iteration methods

The Update rule is given by solving a **constrained optimization problem**:

$$\max_{\delta\theta} \nabla_{\theta} J(\theta)^T \delta\theta \quad \text{subject to} \quad D_{\text{KL}}(\pi_{\theta} \parallel \pi_{\theta+\delta\theta}) \leq \epsilon,$$

where D_{KL} is the Kullback-Leibler divergence that enforces a trust region constraint.

We can use Taylor expansion of 2nd order to approximate KL-Divergence term:

$$D_{\text{KL}}(\pi_{\theta} \parallel \pi_{\theta+\delta\theta}) \approx \frac{1}{2} \delta\theta^T F(\theta) \delta\theta,$$

Here, Fisher Information Matrix (FIM) or $F(\theta)$ [13], defined as:

$$F(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{s \sim d^{\pi_\theta}, a \sim \pi_\theta} [\nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta(a | s) \nabla_\theta \log \pi_\theta(a | s)^\top], [13]$$

with $d^{\pi_\theta}(s)$ which tells us how often a state s is visited under policy π , weighted by a discount factor γ (i.e. **discounted state visitation distribution**)

The final natural gradient update can be written as:

$$\theta \leftarrow \theta + \alpha F(\theta)^{-1} \nabla_\theta J(\theta),$$

where α is the learning rate and $F(\theta)^{-1} \nabla_\theta J(\theta)$ is the direction of natural gradient.

Compared to standard gradient ascent rule, this is a much better approach as it accounts for the curvature of the policy space. This method ensures stability and is sample efficient as well. We use Natural Policy Gradient as a theoretical foundation for advanced policy optimization algorithms like Trust Region Policy Optimization (TRPO) and Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) later on in the thesis

3.2.3 Trust Region Policy Optimization (TRPO)

Trust Region Policy Optimization (TRPO) (Schulman et al. [21]) method builds upon Natural Policy Gradient (NPG) and improves it further by enforcing a trust region constraint. The Trust region constraint will ensure that the new update for policy during training doesn't deviate much from the current policy. Schulman et al. [21] shows this leads to more stable and monotonic policy updates. Inverting the Fisher's Matrix in NPG is computationally expensive, instead TRPO solves the following constrained optimization problem:

$$\max \mathbb{E}_{s \sim \rho^{\pi_{\theta_k}}, a \sim \pi_{\theta_k}} \left[\frac{\pi_\theta(a|s)}{\pi_{\theta_k}(a|s)} \hat{\mathcal{A}}^{\pi_{\theta_k}}(s, a) \right], [21]$$

subject to

$$\mathbb{E}_{s \sim \rho^{\pi_{\theta_k}}} [\mathcal{D}_{KL}(\pi_{\theta_k} || \pi_\theta(\cdot | s))] \leq \delta, [21]$$

The **Objective** comes from a surrogate advantage function, which is based on importance sampling

The Main bottlenecks of TRPO method:

- TRPO requires solving a constrained optimization problem using a **Second-Order Method**(typically conjugate gradient)
- The computation of KL-Divergence term is hard in practice.

This motivates the use of clipping in the PPO algorithm which performs the same job but in a much more computationally efficient way

3.2.4 Proximal Policy Optimization(PPO)

Proximal Policy Optimization(PPO)[22] introduced in Schulman et al. [22] is an extension to TRPO method which retains the core idea of TRPO(trust region constraint) while addressing the main bottlenecks of TRPO. It's a first-order optimization algorithm and eliminates the need for KL constraint. PPO replaces the constrained optimization objective in TRPO with a ***clipped surrogate objective*** Schulman et al. [22]:

$$Loss^{CLIP}(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_t \left[\min \left(r_t(\theta) \hat{\mathcal{A}}_t, \text{clip}(r_t(\theta), 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon) \hat{\mathcal{A}}_t \right) \right], \text{Schulman et al. [22]}$$

where:

- where probability ratio: $r_t(\theta) = \frac{\pi_{\theta}(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_{old}(a_t|s_t)}$
- ϵ is a hyperparameter that can be tuned.

In this way, PPO prevents large policy updates without requiring hard KL constraint. Below is the complete for PPO algorithm adapted from Schulman et al. [22]:

Algorithm 2 Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) (Adapted from Schulman et al. [22])

Require: Policy π_θ , value network V_ϕ , learning rates η_θ, η_ϕ , clip factor ϵ

```
1: while training do
2:   Roll out trajectories using current policy  $\pi_\theta$ , store data in buffer  $\mathcal{D}$ 
3:   Compute advantage estimates  $\hat{A}_t$  (e.g., via GAE), and returns  $\hat{R}_t$ 
4:   for multiple epochs do
5:     for each minibatch from  $\mathcal{D}$  do
6:       Ratio:  $r_t = \frac{\pi_\theta(a_t|s_t)}{\pi_{\theta_{\text{old}}}(a_t|s_t)}$ 
7:       Surrogate loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{PPO}} = \mathbb{E} \left[ \min(r_t \hat{A}_t, \text{clip}(r_t, 1-\epsilon, 1+\epsilon) \hat{A}_t) \right]$$

8:       Update  $\theta \leftarrow \theta + \eta_\theta \nabla_\theta \mathcal{L}_{\text{PPO}}$ 
9:       Value loss:  $\mathcal{L}_V = \mathbb{E} \left[ (V_\phi(s_t) - \hat{R}_t)^2 \right]$ 
10:      Update  $\phi \leftarrow \phi - \eta_\phi \nabla_\phi \mathcal{L}_V$ 
11:     end for
12:   end for
13:   Sync old policy:  $\theta_{\text{old}} \leftarrow \theta$ 
14: end while
```

3.2.5 Soft Actor-Critic Methods(SAC)

So far, the policy gradient methods that we have seen NPG, TRPO and PPO tries to directly maximize the expected return:

$$J(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t r(s_t, a_t) \right]$$

But these methods fall into a category called **on-policy** methods and they all focus on stability of policy updates during training through second order constraints or approximations of them. Even though they are effective and serves the purpose, they suffer from sample efficiency and fails to explore in high-dimensional settings.

In order to address these limitations in on-policy algorithms, Soft Actor-Critic(SAC) was introduced in the paper Haarnoja et al. [8] based on the **max entropy perspective** of RL framework. This augments the reward objective with an additional entropy term

to perform exploration better.

$$J(\pi) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t (r(s_t, a_t) + \alpha \mathcal{H}(\pi(\cdot|s_t))) \right]$$

where $\mathcal{H}(\pi(\cdot|s_t)) = -\mathbb{E}_{a_t \sim \pi} [\log \pi(a_t|s_t)]$ is the policy entropy, and $\alpha > 0$ is a temperature parameter which controls the trade-off between maximizing reward (exploitation) and entropy (exploration)

Haarnoja et al. [8] is an off-policy method which means it maintains a replay buffer collected from a policy at a particular step and use the buffer to update the policy. Haarnoja et al. [8] uses an **actor-critic architecture** with two separate networks (i.e. actor and critic). As described in Haarnoja et al. [8], SAC algorithm uses the following objectives:

$$J(\pi) = \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \mathbb{E}_{(s_t, a_t) \sim \rho_{\pi}} [r(s_t, a_t) + \alpha \mathcal{H}(\pi(\cdot|s_t))] \quad (3.2)$$

The **Soft-Q Function** is defined as:

$$Q^{\pi}(s_t, a_t) = \mathbb{E}_{\tau \sim \pi} \left[\sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \gamma^l (r(s_{t+l}, a_{t+l}) + \alpha \mathcal{H}(\pi(\cdot|s_{t+l}))) \right] \quad (3.3)$$

We train the Critic Network or Q-Network by minimizing the following **Soft Bellman Residual** term:

$$\mathcal{L}_Q(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{(s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1}) \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\left(Q_{\theta}(s_t, a_t) - \hat{Q}(s_t, a_t) \right)^2 \right] \quad (3.4)$$

Target value for this is given by:

$$\hat{Q}(s_t, a_t) = r_t + \gamma \mathbb{E}_{a_{t+1} \sim \pi} [Q_{\bar{\theta}}(s_{t+1}, a_{t+1}) - \alpha \log \pi(a_{t+1}|s_{t+1})] \quad (3.5)$$

Here, $\bar{\theta}$ denotes the parameters of a target Q-network.

The actor network is trained to **maximize the soft Q-value** while maximizing entropy:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\pi}(\phi) = \mathbb{E}_{s_t \sim \mathcal{D}} \left[\mathbb{E}_{a_t \sim \pi_{\phi}} [\alpha \log \pi_{\phi}(a_t|s_t) - Q_{\theta}(s_t, a_t)] \right] \quad (3.6)$$

We can also dynamically adjust the temperature α . The last policy objective encourages actions which have high expected value and high entropy to naturally facilitate exploration-exploitation trade-off in SAC. The complete SAC algorithm from the paper Haarnoja et al. [8]:

Algorithm 3 Soft Actor-Critic (Adapted from Haarnoja et al. [8])

Require: Initialize $Q_{\theta_1}, Q_{\theta_2}$, actor π_ϕ , target networks $\bar{\theta}_1, \bar{\theta}_2 \leftarrow \theta_1, \theta_2$, entropy parameter α , and buffer \mathcal{D}

- 1: **while** not converged **do**
 - 2: Observe s_t ; sample $a_t \sim \pi_\phi(\cdot|s_t)$; step env to get r_t, s_{t+1} ; store transition in \mathcal{D}
 - 3: Sample batch $\{(s, a, r, s')\}$ from \mathcal{D} ; sample $a' \sim \pi_\phi(\cdot|s')$
 - 4: $y \leftarrow r + \gamma (\min_j Q_{\bar{\theta}_j}(s', a') - \alpha \log \pi_\phi(a'|s'))$
 - 5: Update Q_{θ_j} by minimizing $\mathbb{E}[(Q_{\theta_j}(s, a) - y)^2]$, for $j = 1, 2$
 - 6: Update π_ϕ via $\nabla_\phi \mathbb{E}[\alpha \log \pi_\phi(a|s) - \min_j Q_{\theta_j}(s, a)]$
 - 7: Update α (optional): $\nabla_\alpha \mathbb{E}[-\alpha \log \pi_\phi(a|s) - \alpha \mathcal{H}]$
 - 8: Soft-update targets: $\bar{\theta}_j \leftarrow \tau \theta_j + (1 - \tau) \bar{\theta}_j$
 - 9: **end while**
-

3.3 Taxonomical Sketch of RL Algorithms

Figure 3.1: Taxonomical Sketch of RL Algorithms

To conclude our review of reinforcement learning algorithms, we can organize them into a taxonomy based on the different problem settings they are designed to address. One of the most fundamental ways to distinguish among these settings is by asking: **Do we know the model of the environment?** More formally, this refers to whether the transition dynamics $\mathcal{P}(s'|s, a)$ - which tells us the probability of landing in a new state s' after taking an action a in state s - are known or not

When the model is **known**, we have access to the full dynamics of the environment. This opens the door to planning-based methods, which rely on using the model directly to compute optimal behavior.

For Small MDPs, when the state space and action spaces are small, we can solve the MDP exactly using tabular methods: **Policy Iteration** and **Value Iteration** are classic dynamic programming that compute optimal policies by sweeping over the state space

For Large MDPs, in large state spaces, these exact methods doesn't scale since it's no longer possible to maintain a full tables of values. We can use approximate methods: ***Approximate Dynamic Programming***, which uses function approximation (e.g. neural networks) to generalize across states and actions

When the environment dynamics are not known, we rely on **model-free methods** that learn from sampled interactions. In Model-free, we come across three broad categories: **Value-Based Methods, Policy-Based Methods, Actor-Critic Methods**

To conclude our exploration of reinforcement learning algorithms, it's important to highlight a key distinction that plays a central role in how these methods learn: the on-policy vs off-policy paradigm. This distinction hinges on whether the policy used to collect experiences is the same as the policy being updated.

- **On-Policy methods:** such as PPO, TRPO, and REINFORCE, require samples from the current policy at every update
- **Off-Policy methods:** can reuse older samples from experience replay buffers, making them more sample-efficient.

With this understanding, we now focus on three important algorithms that cover both discrete and continuous action spaces, and represent different ways of learning from data (on-policy and off-policy). These methods are especially well-suited for handling the challenges of non-stationary MDPs in Continual Reinforcement Learning:

- **Rainbow DQN:** An *off-policy* method for *discrete action spaces*
- **Proximal Policy Optimization(PPO):** An *on-policy* method that handles both *discrete and continuous action spaces*
- **Soft Actor-Critic(SAC):** An *off-policy* method for *continuous control*

These three algorithms represent the key approaches in reinforcement learning, and they will form the core of the methodology in this thesis.

Part II: Continual Reinforcement Learning

Chapter 4

Literature Review of Continual RL

Continual learning (learning from non-stationary data distributions) involves learning from samples of different distributions (coming from different tasks) that arrive in a sequence. A continual learning model, commonly a neural network parametrized by θ needs to learn a sequence of tasks with no or limited access to old training samples. One of the major challenges for deep learning methods (neural network based) when learning over a non-stationary data stream is *stability-plasticity dilemma*. A common problem we encounter in continual learning is called *catastrophic forgetting* problem (McCloskey and Cohen [17]), where the network adapts to recent experiences while significantly deteriorating its capabilities on past experiences. The literature shows that while replay-based methods help mitigate catastrophic forgetting, learning-to-adapt approaches enable forward transfer from previous tasks to subsequent tasks. As you can see from the taxonomy tree in the figure 4.1, in this thesis we suggest the method, *Look Ahead MAML (LaMAML)* that has both characteristics, i.e. replay-based and learning to adapt

Figure 4.1: Taxonomy of Continual RL Methods

4.1 Replay Based Methods

Experience replay methods or simply replay methods reinforce the importance of experiences from the past distribution during continual RL(Lin [16]). Replay methods help adjust our model by using past data as a proxy for future data—as long as past patterns are similar to future ones. Because of this, replay methods has shown promise for tackling continual RL. However these methods doesn’t scale well as the memory requirements grow with increasing number of tasks

4.2 Learning to Adapt

Learning to learn methods is a paradigm where the model provide good inductive biases(or starting priors) to the learning process that improves sample efficiency during adaptation to new tasks. Thrun et al. [26] introduced self-modifying policies which provides a general framework for these approaches in continual RL. In Deep RL, many of the works have adopted a simpler meta-optimization which is based on the ideas of *meta-training* and *meta-testing*. A simple illustration of this kind of inner-loop and outer-loop optimization

is shown in the figure 4.2 below

Figure 4.2: Bi-Level Optimization Process (Inner Loop and Outer Loop)

4.2.1 Meta-Learning Algorithms for RL

In meta-learning algorithms for reinforcement learning, we are interested in **learning a policy initialization** that can rapidly adapt to new tasks with few gradient updates. We approach continual RL/Non-stationary MDPs from meta-learning perspective in order to solve the *forward and backward transfer* issues in continual learning setup discussed in Chapter 4. In this framework, the main components are:

Task Distribution and Sampling

Let $p(\mathcal{T})$ denote distribution over tasks, where each task $\tau \in \mathcal{T}$ is an MDP defined as:

$$\tau = (\mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}_\tau(s'|s, a), r_\tau(s, a), \gamma)$$

At each iteration, a batch of tasks $\{\tau_i\}_{i=1}^B \sim p(\mathcal{T})$ is sampled independently

Inner Loop: Task-Specific Adaptation

Given a policy π_θ parameterized by θ , the goal is to perform *task-specific adaptation* using experience from each task.

For task τ_i , we collect trajectories $\mathcal{D}_{\tau_i}^{\text{train}}$ by executing π_θ , and compute the task-specific

loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}(\theta) = -\mathbb{E}_{\pi_\theta} \left[\sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \gamma^t r_{\tau_i}(s_t, a_t) \right]. \quad (4.1)$$

A single *inner update* using policy gradient (or actor-critic) is given by:

$$\theta'_i = \theta - \alpha \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}(\theta), \quad (4.2)$$

where α is the inner-loop learning rate.

In practice, $k > 1$ inner steps may be used:

$$\theta_i^{(j+1)} = \theta_i^{(j)} - \alpha \nabla_{\theta_i^{(j)}} \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}(\theta_i^{(j)}), \quad \theta_i^{(0)} = \theta. \quad (4.3)$$

Outer Loop: Meta-Objective and Optimization

After adaptation, the model is evaluated on a *held-out validation set* $\mathcal{D}_{\tau_i}^{\text{val}} \sim \pi_{\theta'_i}$. The *meta-objective* then becomes:

$$\min_{\theta} \sum_{i=1}^B \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}^{\text{meta}}(\theta'_i) = \sum_{i=1}^B \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}(\theta - \alpha \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}(\theta)). \quad (4.4)$$

This leads to a *bilevel optimization* structure:

- **Inner level:** Compute θ'_i using training data from task τ_i ,
- **Outer level:** Update θ based on validation performance of θ'_i .

The outer update gradient requires *second-order derivatives*:

$$\nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}(\theta'_i) = \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}(\theta - \alpha \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}(\theta)), \quad (4.5)$$

which MAML computes exactly (full second-order), or approximately (first-order MAML or FOMAML).

The formulation of meta-learning represents the general structure of **bi-level optimization**. In the subsequent sections, we build upon this and refine the meta-objective that is equivalent to solving continual RL objective and ultimately arrive at **Look Ahead MAML approach**

Given the task distribution is non-stationary and presented as a stream

$$\tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3, \dots, \tau_t, \dots,$$

Our main goals in continual RL as we discussed in chapter 4:

- **Forward Transfer:** Adapt rapidly to current task τ_t and transfer knowledge to unseen tasks in future
- **Backward Transfer:** Retain performance on previously encountered tasks $\{\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_{t-1}\}$

In this chapter, we give motivation for the use of meta-learning algorithms (**Look Ahead MAML** proposed in Gupta et al. [7]) which focuses on gradient alignment and per-parameter learnable inner-loop rates (α_i^j) for solving the above two goals in continual reinforcement learning. We analyze the algorithm and showcase that Look Ahead MAML (Gupta et al. [7]) which has been previously used in supervised learning setting can also work well in the reinforcement learning setting.

Model-Agnostic Meta-Learning(MAML) for Fast Adapatation of Deep Networks

Model-Agnostic Meta Learning algorithm(or MAML) proposed in Finn et al. [6] is a meta-optimization based algorithm which can work with any model that learns through gradient descent.

Given f_θ with parameters θ and a task τ_i along with samples of data associated with the task. The update rule for one step is given as

$$\theta'_i = \theta - \alpha \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}^{(0)}(f_\theta)$$

where $\mathcal{L}^{(0)}$ is the loss computed using the initial mini data batch

Figure 4.3: Diagram of MAML (Source: Finn et al. [6])

The update rule above only updates for one task whereas in our meta learning problem setting we have \mathcal{M} such tasks. To achieve a better generalization across a different tasks, our objective is to find a good θ^* that act as a good inductive prior in learning a given task. Essentially, through this we are finding a good initial set of parameters to begin with for the task-specific adaptation to converge faster. Now for a new batch of data, the loss $\mathcal{L}^{(1)}$ depends on next mini-batch(mini-batches are sampled from our dataset). The update rule will be,

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} \sum_{\tau_i \sim p(\tau)} \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}^{(1)}(f_{\theta'_i}) = \arg \min_{\theta} \sum_{\tau_i \sim p(\tau)} \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}^{(1)}(f_{\theta - \alpha \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}^{(0)}(f_{\theta})})$$

$$\theta \leftarrow \theta - \beta \nabla_{\theta} \sum_{\tau_i \sim p(\tau)} \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}^{(1)}(f_{\theta - \alpha \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\tau_i}^{(0)}(f_{\theta})})$$

And the Corresponding algorithm from the original paper : Finn et al. [6]

Algorithm 4 Meta-Learning via Gradient-Based Task Adaptation (Adapted from MAML Finn et al. [6])

Require: $p(\mathcal{T})$: distribution over learning tasks

Require: α, β : learning rates for inner and outer updates

- 1: Initialize model parameters θ randomly
- 2: **while** meta-training not converged **do**
- 3: Sample a set of tasks $\{\mathcal{T}_i\}$ from $p(\mathcal{T})$
- 4: **for all** task \mathcal{T}_i in the sampled batch **do**
- 5: Sample a small training dataset $\mathcal{D}_i^{\text{train}}$ for adaptation
- 6: Compute loss $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}_i}^{\text{train}}(f_\theta)$ on this set
- 7: Compute adapted task-specific parameters via gradient step:

$$\theta'_i \leftarrow \theta - \alpha \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}_i}^{\text{train}}(f_\theta)$$

- 8: // These adapted parameters are specific to task \mathcal{T}_i
- 9: **end for**
- 10: // Meta-objective computed using a separate validation set
- 11: For each task \mathcal{T}_i , evaluate meta-loss on $\mathcal{D}_i^{\text{val}}$ using $f_{\theta'_i}$
- 12: Compute meta-gradient:

$$\nabla_{\theta} \sum_i \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}_i}^{\text{val}}(f_{\theta'_i})$$

- 13: Update shared parameters using gradient descent:

$$\theta \leftarrow \theta - \beta \nabla_{\theta} \sum_i \mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}_i}^{\text{val}}(f_{\theta'_i})$$

- 14: // This update improves the initial parameters θ so they adapt well across tasks
 - 15: **end while**
-

First-Order MAML(FOMAML)

Outer Loop computation is performed with new data batch for updating meta-objective from a distribution of tasks

$$\theta_{meta} \leftarrow \theta_{meta} - \beta \nabla_{\theta} \mathcal{L}^{(1)}(\theta_k) \quad : \text{update for meta - objective}$$

where $\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}^{(1)}(\theta_k)$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \nabla_{\theta_k}\mathcal{L}^{(1)}(\theta_k) \cdot (\nabla_{\theta_{k-1}}\theta_k) \cdots (\nabla_{\theta_0}\theta_1) \cdot (\nabla_{\theta}\theta_0) \quad ; \text{ following the chain rule} \\
&= \nabla_{\theta_k}\mathcal{L}^{(1)}(\theta_k) \cdot \left(\prod_{i=1}^k \nabla_{\theta_{i-1}}\theta_i \right) \cdot I \\
&= \nabla_{\theta_k}\mathcal{L}^{(1)}(\theta_k) \cdot \prod_{i=1}^k \nabla_{\theta_{i-1}} (\theta_{i-1} - \alpha \nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}^{(0)}(\theta_{i-1})) \\
&= \nabla_{\theta_k}\mathcal{L}^{(1)}(\theta_k) \cdot \prod_{i=1}^k (I - \alpha \nabla_{\theta_{i-1}}(\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}^{(0)}(\theta_{i-1})))
\end{aligned}$$

A simplified expression of the meta-gradient after k adaptation steps is given by:

$$g_{\text{meta}} = \nabla_{\theta_k}\mathcal{L}^{(1)}(\theta_k) \cdot \prod_{i=1}^k (I - \alpha \nabla_{\theta_{i-1}}(\nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}^{(0)}(\theta_{i-1}))) \quad (4.6)$$

Here, θ_k denotes the parameter vector after k inner updates, α is the inner-loop learning rate, and the product of Jacobian-related terms captures how each inner update step influences the outer meta-loss. The inner gradient term reflects second-order effects due to adaptation.

The first-order MAML approach ignores the second derivative part in Equation (3.6). We introduce this method as the foundation for the LaMAML approach, a first-order variant of MAML for continual reinforcement learning.

Gradient Interference and Alignment Problem

In continual RL, the learning agent comes across a stream of non-stationary MDP environments during the learning process and it will keep on updating its policy. Each update step is based on gradients computed from the current task, but these gradients can interfere with one another during any two consecutive tasks. This phenomenon is called gradient interference. Mathematically speaking, For a given time step the agent is trained on task \mathcal{T}_i and computes a gradient:

$$g_i = \nabla_{\theta}\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}_i}(\theta)$$

where θ denotes the policy parameters and $\mathcal{L}_{\mathcal{T}_i}(\theta)$ is loss for task \mathcal{T}_i . In continual RL, across tasks we collect gradients $\{g_i\}$ for different tasks sequentially. Since the non-stationary environments in these tasks the gradients do not point in similar directions in the parameter space. The alignment between gradients can be measured by dot-product

$$g_i^T g_j$$

between gradients of tasks i and j or robustly, we can compute cosine similarity:

$$\cos \theta_{ij} = \frac{g_i^T g_j}{\|g_i\| \|g_j\|}$$

When $\cos \theta_{ij} > 0$, the gradients are aligned and we can interpret this as learning updates for one task are likely to help other or forward transfer takes place. But when $\cos \theta_{ij} < 0$, the updates conflict - improving performance on task \mathcal{T}_i may degrade performance on task \mathcal{T}_j i.e. *Catastrophic Forgetting* as briefly discussed in the continual learning methods section

Solving this "gradient interference" problem will enable us to learn using samples from different tasks and updating the model parameters without forgetting what was learned in the previous task thus reducing *Catastrophic Forgetting* issue

Chapter 5

Proposed Method: La-MAML

5.1 Look-Ahead MAML Approach

Gupta et al. [7] introduced Look Ahead MAML algorithm which is a first-order MAML based approach for continual learning that does one step look ahead and computes what the updated gradients might be after one more gradient updates for each task. By comparing the next gradient updates among different tasks, the algorithm can assess the alignment (or misalignment) between them. In continual learning settings, if the gradients from different tasks point in conflicting directions (i.e. Negative dot-product or low cosine similarity), then updating the parameters using raw gradients may lead to catastrophic forgetting. The Look Ahead mechanism helps to realign the gradients during learning process between tasks. The algorithm implicitly penalizes updates that would worsen performance on previously learned tasks and instead reinforces update directions in the parameter space that benefits all tasks

Equivalence of Meta-Learning and Continual Learning Objectives Riemer et al. [20] showed the equivalence of optimizing the continual learning objective of minimizing loss on and aligning gradients between a set of tasks $\tau_{1:t}$ came across till time j can be optimized by First Order MAML like Objective(*on the right*)

$$\min_{\theta_0^j} \left(\sum_{i=1}^t \ell_i(\theta_0^j) - \alpha \sum_{p,q \leq t} \left(\frac{\partial \ell_p(\theta_0^j)}{\partial \theta_0^j} \cdot \frac{\partial \ell_q(\theta_0^j)}{\partial \theta_0^j} \right) \right) = \min_{\theta_0^j} \mathbb{E}_{\pi_{1:t}} [L_t(U_k(\theta_0^j))] \quad (5.1)$$

[7] where the *meta-loss* $\mathcal{L}_t = \sum_{i=1}^t \ell_i$ is evaluated on samples from tasks $\tau_{1:t}$. This implies that we can use the meta-objective that learn a good initialization across tasks as a proxy

for learning optimal parameters in continual learning

We develop an intermediate step called **C-MAML** before reaching to **La-MAML** Method. We define C-MAML objective as

$$\min_{\theta_0^j} \Sigma_{\mathcal{S}_k^k \sim \mathcal{D}_t} \left[\mathcal{L}_t(\mathcal{U}_k(\theta_0^j, \mathcal{S}_k^j)) \right] \quad (5.2)$$

where \mathcal{S}_k^j is a stream of k data samples from current task τ_t at time j . The meta-loss \mathcal{L}_t is evaluated on θ_0^j . Gupta et al. [7] shows the equivalence between optimising the objective in Equation (5.2) and objective in the popular continual learning approach **A-GEM** proposed in Chaudhry et al. [4] as:

$$\min_{\theta_0^j} \mathbb{E}_{\pi_{1:t}} [L_t(U_k(\theta_0^j))] = \min_{\theta_0^j} \sum_{i=1}^t \left(\ell_i(\theta_0^j) - \alpha \frac{\partial \ell_i(\theta_0^j)}{\partial \theta_0^j} \cdot \frac{\partial \ell_i(\theta_0^j)}{\partial \theta_0^j} \right). \quad (5.3)$$

Meta-objective function with an alignment regularization term, penalizing gradient self-interference across tasks in continual learning from Gupta et al. [7].

This differs from Equation (5.1) because this focuses on aligning the gradients of τ_i and the average gradient of $\tau_{1:t}$ instead of aligning all the pair-wise gradients between tasks $\tau_{1:t}$.

In **Look Ahead MAML**, the authors propose to include a set of trainable **per-parameter learning rates (LRs)** in the *inner updates* as shows in the Figure (5.1) below. Look Ahead MAML extends the previously derived objective for reducing gradient interference and facilitate gradient alignment between tasks to incorporate learnable per-parameter learning rates. Now the augmented objective for La-MAML becomes:

$$\min_{\theta_0^j, \alpha^j} \Sigma_{\mathcal{S}_k^k \sim \mathcal{D}_t} \left[\mathcal{L}_t(\mathcal{U}_k(\alpha^j, \theta_0^j, \mathcal{S}_k^j)) \right] \quad (5.4)$$

Figure 5.1: Look Ahead MAML proposed in Gupta et al. [7]

Now we derive the ∇ of this objective with respect θ_0^j and LRs α^j at time step j with \mathcal{L}_t as meta-loss and where l_t is the *inner-objective*

$$g_{\text{MAML}}(\alpha^j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha^j} (\theta_k^j) \quad (5.5)$$

$$= \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha^j} (U(\theta_{k-1}^j)) \quad (5.6)$$

$$= \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha^j} \left(\theta_{k-1}^j - \alpha^j \frac{\partial \ell_t(\theta_{k-1}^j)}{\partial \theta_{k-1}^j} \right) \right) \quad (5.7)$$

$$= \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \theta_{k-1}^j}{\partial \alpha^j} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha^j} \left(\alpha^j \frac{\partial \ell_t(\theta_{k-1}^j)}{\partial \theta_{k-1}^j} \right) \right) \quad (5.8)$$

$$= \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \theta_{k-1}^j}{\partial \alpha^j} - \frac{\partial \ell_t(\theta_{k-1}^j)}{\partial \theta_{k-1}^j} \right) \quad (5.9)$$

(Take this $\frac{\partial \ell_t(\theta_{k-1}^j)}{\partial \theta_{k-1}^j}$ as constant w.r.t. α^j to obtain the first-order MAML approximation)

$$(5.10)$$

$$= \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha^j} U(\theta_{k-2}^j) - \left(\frac{\partial \ell_t(\theta_{k-1}^j)}{\partial \theta_{k-1}^j} \right) \right) \quad (5.11)$$

$$= \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha^j} \theta_0^j - \sum_{k'=0}^{k-1} \frac{\partial \ell_t(\theta_{k'}^j)}{\partial \theta_{k'}^j} \right) \quad (a)$$

$$= \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) \cdot \left(- \sum_{k'=0}^{k-1} \frac{\partial \ell_t(\theta_{k'}^j)}{\partial \theta_{k'}^j} \right) \quad (b)$$

The gradient of this objective for deriving the update rule will become:

$$g_{\text{MAML}}(\alpha^j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) \cdot \left(- \sum_{k'=0}^{k-1} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_{k'}^j} \ell_t(\theta_{k'}^j) \right). \quad (5.12)$$

Gradient of the MAML objective with respect to learning rate α^j , showing the effect of past task losses on the final gradient in the inner loop.

Similarly, we need to compute $g_{\text{MAML}}(\theta_0^j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_0^j} \mathcal{L}_t(\theta_k^j)$ to derive the MAML gradient for the weights θ_0^j and its first-order approximation will be:

$$g_{\text{MAML}}(\theta_0^j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_0^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) \frac{\partial \theta_k^j}{\partial \theta_0^j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) \frac{\partial U_k(\theta_{k-1}^j)}{\partial \theta_0^j} \quad (5.13)$$

$$= \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_k^j} L_t(\theta_k^j) \frac{\partial \theta_k^j}{\partial \theta_{k-1}^j} \cdots \frac{\partial \theta_1^j}{\partial \theta_0^j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_0^j} U(\theta_1^j) \quad (5.14)$$

(we use chain rule repeatedly $\theta_k^j = U(\theta_{k-1}^j)$)

$$= L'_t(\theta_k^j) (I - \alpha \ell''_t(\theta_{k-1}^j)) \cdots (I - \alpha \ell''_t(\theta_0^j)) \quad (5.15)$$

(using $U'(\theta_k^j) = I - \alpha \ell''_t(\theta_k^j)$ (' implies derivative w.r.t. argument))

$$= \left(\prod_{k'=0}^{k-1} (I - \alpha \ell''_t(\theta_{k'}^j)) \right) L'_t(\theta_k^j) \quad (5.16)$$

Set all the first-order gradient terms as constants since computation of second-order derivatives is computationally expensive, then the first-order approximation will be:

$$g_{\text{FOMAML}}(\theta_0^j) = \left(\prod_{k'=0}^{k-1} (I - \alpha \ell''_t(\theta_{k'}^j)) \right) L'_t(\theta_k^j) = L'_t(\theta_k^j) \quad (5.17)$$

The paper [7] proposed updating the network weights and Learning Rates *asynchronously* in the meta-update:

$$\theta_0^{j+1} \leftarrow \theta_0^j - \max(0, \alpha^{j+1}) \cdot \nabla_{\theta_0^j} \mathcal{L}_t(\theta_k^j) \quad (5.18)$$

where k is the number of steps taken in the inner-loop. We obtain α^{j+1} by performing SGD (Stochastic Gradient Descent) update with the gradient of Learning Rate (LR) from Equation (5.12) at time j and substitute $\nabla_{\theta_0^j} \mathcal{L}_t(\theta_k^j)$ with g_{MAML} or g_{FOMAML} from Equation (5.16) or Equation (5.17), the latter one if we want to use a first-order approximation to avoid expensive computation of second-order derivatives

The meta-objective adjusts how fast and in what direction the model learns, and

this helps in adapting more quickly to new tasks while still retaining previous tasks i.e. avoiding catastrophic forgetting.

A small implementation detail is the use of reservoir sampling on the inbound stream of samples during training and populating a **Replay Buffer (R)**. For each meta-update, a **batch** b of data samples is sampled from the current task. This is combined with another batch from the **replay buffer R** to create a **meta-batch** b_m , which is union of samples from both old and current tasks. Here, the parameters θ_0^j are updated over k inner steps using samples from b , one at a time. The meta-loss $\mathcal{L}_t(\theta_j^k)$ is computed on b_m so as to infer how well the new parameter set after update performs across all tasks seen till that point. That is why the method is considered to incorporate replay-based learning as well.

The clipping of learning rates are performed to avoid positive values to avoid *gradient ascent* and interfering parameter updates. The LRs adjust how parameters are updated based on the interaction between current task and old tasks from replay. The LRs can increase or decrease with every new task that come in, which is similar to trust-region methods or look-ahead strategies.

With the conclusion of analysis of Look Ahead MAML we now have a continual learning method that can be applied to the Loss functions of the algorithms derived in the Part I (Current Methods) of this thesis i.e. **PPO, SAC, Rainbow DQN**

Note: *We have already discussed our motivation for choosing these three algorithms from the RL landscape in Chapter 3*

5.2 La-MAML with PPO, SAC and Rainbow DQN Algorithm

In LaMAML, the main novelty is the use of a learnable inner-loop learning rates (LR) that is adjusted by the alignment between gradients from current and replayed data. This same framework can be used to perform inner updates for the base RL algorithms by formulating the meta-objectives for these algorithms just like the derivations above. Below we describe the adaptation for PPO, SAC, and Rainbow DQN.

First we derive the inner-losses and meta losses which are different for all three algorithms and the rest of the Look Ahead MAML framework will take these l_{inner} and L_{meta} and does the bi-level optimization for continual RL

For PPO Algorithm:

Inner loss (clipped surrogate):

$$\ell_{inner}^{\text{PPO}}(\theta; D) = -\mathbb{E}_{(s,a)\sim D} \left[\min(r_\theta \hat{A}, \text{clip}(r_\theta, 1 - \epsilon, 1 + \epsilon) \hat{A}) \right], \quad r_\theta = \frac{\pi_\theta(a | s)}{\pi_{\text{old}}(a | s)}.$$

Meta loss:

$$L_{\text{meta}}^{\text{PPO}}(\theta_k) = \sum_{i=1}^t \ell_{inner}^{\text{PPO}}(\theta_k; D_i).$$

For SAC Algorithm:

Let $\Psi = (\phi, \theta, \tau)$ collect the critic, actor, and temperature.

Inner loss (SAC):

$$\ell_{inner}^{\text{SAC}}(\Psi; D) = J_Q(\phi; D) + J_\pi(\theta; \phi, D) + J_\tau(\tau; \theta, D),$$

with

$$J_Q(\phi) = \mathbb{E}_{(s,a,r,s')\sim D} \left[(Q_\phi(s, a) - y)^2 \right], \quad y = r + \gamma [\bar{Q}_\phi(s', a') - \tau \log \pi_\theta(a' | s')],$$

$$J_\pi(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{s\sim D, a\sim\pi_\theta} [\tau \log \pi_\theta(a | s) - Q_\phi(s, a)],$$

$$J_\tau(\tau) = \mathbb{E}_{s\sim D, a\sim\pi_\theta} [-\tau (\log \pi_\theta(a | s) + \bar{H})].$$

Meta loss:

$$L_{\text{meta}}^{\text{SAC}}(\Psi_k) = \sum_{i=1}^t \ell_{\text{inner}}^{\text{SAC}}(\Psi_k; D_i).$$

For Rainbow-DQN Algorithm:

Let $p_\theta(s, a) \in \Delta^N$ be the predicted distribution over N atoms $\{z_i\}$.

Inner loss (distributional cross-entropy):

$$\ell_{\text{inner}}^{\text{Rainbow}}(\theta; B) = \mathbb{E}_{(s,a,r,s') \sim B} \left[- \sum_{i=1}^N [\text{proj}_{\{z_i\}}(r + \gamma z'_i)]_i \log p_\theta(s, a)_i \right].$$

Meta loss:

$$L_{\text{meta}}^{\text{Rainbow}}(\theta_k) = \sum_{i=1}^t \ell_{\text{inner}}^{\text{Rainbow}}(\theta_k; B_i).$$

La-MAML Framework

We seek parameters θ and per-parameter step-sizes α to minimize over tasks $1, \dots, T$:

$$\min_{\theta, \alpha} \mathbb{E}_{\tau_t} \left[L_{\text{meta}}(U^k(\theta, \alpha; \tau_t)) \right], \quad U(\theta, \alpha; \tau) = \theta - \alpha \odot \nabla_{\theta} \ell_{\text{inner}}(\theta; \tau).$$

Here:

- *Inner loss* ℓ_{inner} is algorithm-specific.
- *Meta loss* $L_{\text{meta}}(\theta_k) = \sum_{i=1}^t \ell_{\text{inner}}(\theta_k; D_i)$ over replayed data.
- *Hypergradient* (first-order):

$$g_\alpha = \frac{\partial L_{\text{meta}}(\theta_k)}{\partial \alpha} = \nabla_{\theta_k} L_{\text{meta}}(\theta_k) \cdot \left(- \sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \nabla_{\theta_j} \ell_{\text{inner}}(\theta_j) \right).$$

- *Asynchronous update*:

$$\alpha \leftarrow \max(0, \alpha - \eta g_\alpha), \quad \theta \leftarrow \theta - \alpha \odot \nabla_{\theta} L_{\text{meta}}(\theta_k).$$

Regardless of the algorithm:

1. Collect new-task batch and replay batches.

2. Adapt for k inner steps: $\theta_{j+1} = \theta_j - \alpha \odot \nabla \ell_{\text{inner}}(\theta_j)$.

3. Compute $g_\alpha = \nabla_{\theta_k} L_{\text{meta}}(\theta_k) \cdot \left(-\sum_{j=0}^{k-1} \nabla_{\theta_j} \ell_{\text{inner}}\right)$.

4. Update:

$$\alpha \leftarrow \max(0, \alpha - \eta g_\alpha), \quad \theta \leftarrow \theta - \alpha \odot \nabla_{\theta} L_{\text{meta}}(\theta_k).$$

This unified approach helps handle non-stationarity in continual RL by aligning gradients across tasks and ensuring robust performance with minimal forgetting. Our Modified Algorithm for Look Ahead MAML (from Gupta et al. [7]) for PPO, SAC and DQN is given as:

Algorithm 5 La-MAML for Continual RL with PPO, SAC, or Rainbow-DQN [Adapted from Gupta et al. [7]]

Require: Initial parameters θ_0 , step-sizes α_0 , inner loss ℓ_{inner} , meta-loss L_{meta} , meta-LR

η

1: Initialize replay buffer $R \leftarrow \emptyset$, outer step $j \leftarrow 0$

2: **for** task $t = 1, \dots, T$ **do**

3: **for** epoch $ep = 1, \dots, n_{\text{ep}}$ **do**

4: **for** batch b from task t **do**

5: $b_m \leftarrow b \cup \text{Sample}(R)$

6: $\theta \leftarrow \theta_0^{(j)}$

7: **for** $n = 0, \dots, |b| - 1$ **do**

8: insert $b[n]$ into R via reservoir sampling

9: $\theta \leftarrow \theta - \alpha^{(j)} \odot \nabla_{\theta} \ell_{\text{inner}}(\theta; b)$ ▷ use PPO surrogate / SAC actor-critic /

Rainbow-DQN loss

10: **end for**

11: $\alpha^{(j+1)} \leftarrow \max(0, \alpha^{(j)} - \eta \nabla_{\alpha} L_{\text{meta}}(\theta; b_m))$

12: $\theta_0^{(j+1)} \leftarrow \theta_0^{(j)} - \alpha^{(j+1)} \odot \nabla_{\theta_0} L_{\text{meta}}(\theta; b_m)$

13: $j \leftarrow j + 1$

14: **end for**

15: **end for**

16: **end for**

Chapter 6

Discussion, Conclusion, and Future Work

6.1 Discussion

Overall, in this thesis we start by defining the RL problem using the MDP model and classical solution methods for MDPs and also discuss thoroughly how we analyze the algorithms in order to choose the representative algorithms from broader RL landscape: PPO for on-policy discrete/continuous action spaces, SAC for off-policy Continuous actions and DQN variant called Rainbow-DQN for Off-Policy Discrete action spaces. In continual RL setting, these algorithms in their original form face the *catastrophic forgetting*(failing to retain performance on old tasks while learning new tasks), backward transfer and forward transfer issues but when augmented with Look Ahead MAML kind of bi-level optimization solves the gradient interference and alignment issue we have when learning multiple tasks sequentially. LookAhead MAML focuses on aligning gradients across old and new tasks which leads to backward transfer (where learning the new task help improve the performance of old tasks) and forward transfer(fast adaptation in learning from old tasks to new tasks) through better inductive priors.

6.2 Conclusions

Look Ahead MAML approach was proposed by Gupta et al. [7] for continual learning in supervised learning setting, but this thesis suggests this method is accurately appropriate

for continual reinforcement learning. Even with major differences in supervised problem setting and RL setting the idea of aligning gradients and usage of a small episodic memory works in continual RL too. We conclude by stating that the chosen method works for CRL setting because it incorporates concepts from both prior-based (from gradient alignment methods) and replay based (from episodic memory replay) approaches.

6.3 Future Work

While this thesis addresses to solve the catastrophic forgetting, forward and backward transfer problem in continual RL there's scope for new avenues in continual RL algorithms. The path forward would be to empirically prove this method on several benchmarks in Continual RL. In RL, the gymnasium environments are used as the standard benchmark for testing new RL algorithms. Our idea is to use a sample of games from the Atari benchmark and test the LaMAML framework with the following algorithms: PPO, SAC and Rainbow DQN. A Theoretical analysis can be done for this framework to obtain convergence guarantees and calculate sample complexity(number of samples required to learn optimal policy per task). Statistical Learning framework can be utilized to analyze different hypothesis classes (function approximation classes or neural networks) and show the capacity of model learning a number of tasks at scale. An analysis can be done on what is the optimal sequence of tasks that can be arranged in the continual RL setup. This can reveal good insights into an adjacent domain called *curriculum reinforcement learning*, where the tasks are organized sequentially from simple to complex goals.

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